

Influence of School Environment on Students Outcomes at Secondary Level

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Abstract

Education plays a vital role in uplifting economic development of the country. It helps to reform a nation or society for the betterment of human life. The main aim of the study was to know the effects of the school environment on students' performance at the secondary level. The study was descriptive in nature. The sample of the study consisted of 36 schools, 12 schools from each district of Sahiwal division. Total 180 teachers were selected as the respondents. The self-developed questionnaire was used as a research instrument. It was found that the school environment, discipline and physical facilities of school have serious effects on students' performance. The different measures of school environment like conducive classroom environment, peaceful classroom environment, peaceful school environment, safe and secure school environment, teaching techniques, professional qualification of teachers, peer groups, classroom activities, physical facilities (electricity, drinking water, audio visual aids, school building, school furniture), absenteeism, preparation of lesson plans, malpractices during examinations, illegal funds collection, school discipline affects students' personality, good behavior between school and society, teacher students' relationship, school visits and teachers' attitude affects students' learning.

Keywords: Performance, School environment, Effects, Secondary level, academic problems.

Introduction

The environment is the totality of what we live in, natural, or constructed spiral, man-made machines, scientific appliances, equipment and natural conditions such as air, water, and land which directly and indirectly affect human beings. The school environment is the result of the interaction of teachers- students' relationship, teachers' academic and professional qualification, teachers' teaching experience, availability and utilization of physical facilities and learning materials, as well as socio- economic background of students and other activities undertaken for achieving its objectives. It includes classrooms, science laboratories, workshops, libraries, gardens, playgrounds and equipment, etc. to the schools.

Entwisle (2018) described that the environment plays a vital role in the personality development of the students. A proper and conducive environment is very much necessary for fruitful learning of the children. Especially home and educational institutions should provide necessary stimulus for the learning experience. The child spends most of his time in school, and here his environment is exerting a different influence on performance through curricula, teaching techniques, and relationship. As students are the backbones of the nation, it is important to maintain a healthy school environment.

Mick (2011) stated that school environment consists of many areas including school settings, the safety of students, teachers, head and services supporting staff, plants, physical and instructional facilities, fairness and adequacy of disciplinary procedures. It also includes an attractive school building, properly ventilated classrooms with required electric appliances, well equipped laboratory, library, sufficient furniture, audio-visual aids, hygienic conditions, and playground, etc. It helps in energizing and speeding up the whole process of education and can play a leading role for personality development of children. It also helps in improving teaching and learning process.

Maintenance of discipline in classes and educational institutions is the action taken by a teacher or the school heads towards a student/ students when their behavior disrupts the ongoing educational activity or breaks the rules and regulations. It helps to control the wrong done by the students, or they cross their limits. It indicates expected standards of clothing, timekeeping, social conduct, moral and ethical values. It is an

application of the punishment that is the consequences of breaking the rules by the students, so that no indiscipline issue develops in the institution, as it proves harmful or against school policies, educational norms or school traditions.

Indiscipline among teachers is their acts of behavior that affect effective teaching and learning as well as result of students' academic achievement. Common indiscipline behavior by teachers include; absenteeism from school and lesson, lateness, non-preparation of lesson notes, failure to mark students exercise books, non-completion of school records such as diaries, registers, student results, involvement in examination malpractices, illegal collection from parent and students, unapproved study leave with pay, drinking, drug taking and sexual immorality. These are a serious threat to the student.

A proper and adequate environment is very much necessary for fruitful learning of the child. Especially the home and the school should provide the necessary stimulus for the learning experience. The child spends most of his time in school, and here his environment is applying a different influence on performance through curricula, teaching techniques, teacher student relationship. It is clear that if all were well with our educational institutions, all would be well with the nation. Educational institutions are intimately linked with society at large. They are the temples of knowledge.

Schools are the agents of social change and transformation. Therefore, the general condition of our schools, colleges, and universities is a matter of great concern to the nation. Environment plays a vital role in the development of the personality of the students. As a student spends most of his life at school, the school environment is highly responsible for inculcating of great values in him.

Statement of the Problem

It is a fact that policies, curricula, methodologies, and school environment play a vital role in the performance of any educational institution. It is the school environment, which not only helps the teachers to make the teaching- learning process easy, interesting and affective, but it also creates interest among the students, which has a direct impact on the performance of students. But in Punjab province, especially in Central Punjab, since inception of Pakistan, several efforts were made to improve students' performance, by provision of educational facilities to the educational schools, yet most of the secondary schools were lacking in physical and instructional facilities, in turn, it is badly affecting the whole process of education including students' learning outcomes. A healthy school environment can directly improve children's health and effective learning and thereby contribute to the development of healthy adults as skilled and productive members of society.

Research Objectives

1. To find out the effects of the school environment on the performance of secondary school students.
2. To explore the influence of discipline in the school on the performance of students.
3. To find out the effects of school physical facilities on the performance of secondary school students.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of the school environment on students' performance?
2. What is the influence of discipline in school on student's performance?
3. How the physical facilities of the school effect on secondary school students?

The significance of the Study

- This study will be effective for the students, parents, teachers, and all stakeholders of the education department. The study will also be helpful for enhancing the performance of students to know different factors on the performance of students at the secondary level. Students themselves can take help, be stimulating and will enhance the academic achievement of students.

Research Methodology

The researcher had used a quantitative method to complete the study. The study was descriptive in nature, so the survey technique was used to collect data for the study. All the secondary school teachers (9123) of three districts of southern Punjab, i.e., Pakpattan, Sahiwal, and Okara were the populations of the study. The researcher had selected the sample of the study at the rate of 7% from the target population. Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of the sample of the study. Keeping in view the effect of the

school environment on the performance of students at the secondary level the researcher had designed a questionnaire for getting quantitative data from selected respondents of three districts of central Punjab.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample

Sr. No	Districts	School Distribution			Sample Distribution		
		Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1.	Okara	06	06	12	30	30	60
2.	Sahiwal	06	06	12	30	30	60
3.	Pakpattan	06	06	12	30	30	60
	Total	18	18	36	90	90	180

Review of the Related Literature

Johnson et al., (2012) described this is because; schools with a good and conducive environment that has the best type of teachers, instructional materials and physical facilities will produce better school leavers with high achievement. Most at times parents of students are not satisfied with the facilities provided in their school. Also, the level at which some teachers, show a high level of indiscipline does not seem to depict them as role models. They somewhat encourage indiscipline among students by their attitudes. This may have a negative influence on students' performance.

The school environment should have good infrastructural development, adequate trained teachers, good leadership and adequate instructional materials for effective learning (Nwonyuku, 2018). Bua (2013) says that with particular reference to the availability of trained teachers, provision of instructional materials, the motivation of teachers and provision of school physical facilities can raise the students, performance. The influence of the school environment on the academic achievement of students has been an issue of concern to all stakeholders in education.

Heydarian (2015) environment whether physical or virtual, can have an impact on learning. It not only brings people together. It can encourage and facilitate exploration, collaboration, and discussion.

Frimpong et al. (2016) noted that school physical facilities have a significant impact on students' performance. For instance, a reduction in class-size could enhance learning, while the availability of adequate research equipment and teaching material could significantly improve students' performance. They also maintained that student-teacher ratio, physical resources, equipment, and teaching aids have a significant effect on the achievements of students. In the same way, a physical environment with improved facilities provide comfort, security, better understanding of courses and can be dramatic in terms of increased learning and performance.

Culture affects the behavior of teachers, students, staff, and community. It often determines curriculum content. A society's socioeconomic status directly influences its ability to support a learning institution; its ability to attract high caliber teachers with appealing salaries; a safe, secure, and comfortable school environment with all physical facilities; and make available basic needs for students, such as adequate nutrition, health care, adequate rest, and support at home for homework (Bendix, 2017).

Education at the time was designed to provide workers for the emerging factory based, industrial societies and this educational model and organization of schools became known as the "factory model school", with curriculum, teaching style, and assessment heavily uniform and centered around the needs and efficiencies of classroom and teacher management (Lochner et al. 2016). Adelman, (2014) 21st century learning environment is a learning program, plan, and precise content. All are learner-centered and supported by the use of modern arithmetical technologies. Combined learning is a learning program in which a student learns at least in part through the distribution of content and teaching via arithmetical and online media with greater student control over time, place, path, or bound with traditional learning.

School discipline is the actions taken by a teacher or the school organization towards a student when the student's behavior breaks a rule created by the teacher or the school system. Discipline can guide the children's behavior or set limits to help them learn to take care of themselves, other people and the world around them. These rules define the expected standards of clothing, timekeeping, social conduct, and work ethic. The term "discipline" is applied to the punishment that is the consequence of breaking the rules. Discipline suggests

limits restricting certain behaviors or attitudes that are harmful or against school policies, educational norms and school traditions (Kiprop, 2012).

Eisner (2017) studied that have examined the relationship between school environment and student achievement have found that without an environment that supports and recognizes the importance of certain kinds of learning goals, changes and improvements will be the environment of a school, is a key factor in productivity and success. Environment affects what people focus on and what is important to which to pay attention. Yet, there are no quantitative studies that try to disaggregate the various elements of the environment and determine their relationship to student achievement.

The study of Shanjiko, et al. (2017) helps the knowledge that school environment, discipline, and corporeal services have an important effect on academic attainment of secondary schools learners. In secondary school, the students feel intimacy with their teachers, and they make discipline in the classroom. If all were well with our educational institutions, all would be well with the nation.

Khoza (2012) stated that the educational process of development occurs in the physical, social, cultural and psychological environment. A proper and adequate environment is very much necessary for fruitful learning of the child. Especially the home and the school should provide the necessary stimulus for the learning experience. It has great influence in improving the quality of teaching that students of that institution receive and the extent of attention they pay to their lesson and learning in school. A proper and adequate school environment is very much necessary for fruitful learning of the child. The institution that provides a good and peaceful atmosphere for learning to the students and for teaching also can achieve better results and academic achievement from their students, as a child spends most of his daytime in school which is exerting a different influence on performance through curricula, teaching techniques, relationship.

Sithole (2017) said that a number of factors are contributing to the students' poor academic performance in school which may be poor study habits of students, lack of available resource materials, non-conducive school environment, indiscipline, inadequate facilities, teachers ineffectiveness, teaching method and the type of learning environment available for both teachers and students. It also includes indiscipline behavior of teachers include; absenteeism from school and lesson, lateness, non-preparation of lesson notes, failure to mark students exercise books, non-completion of school records such as diaries, registers, student results, involvement in examination malpractices, illegal collection from parent and students, unapproved study leave with pay, drinking, drug taking. These are a serious threat to students' poor performance.

The effectiveness of students' performance depends upon multiple factors like teachers' competencies, students' intake, curriculum standards, and a good school environment. Students' performance is the achievement of the students in any tests or examinations. Conducive school environment has positive impacts on students' performance, while poor environmental conditions have negative impacts, directly reduces their academic performance. School buildings and grounds are the main factors responsible for the academic uplifting of students' performance. They must be designed to provide healthy food items, sanitation, safe water, airy and good lighting rooms, safe playgrounds, violence prevention and emergency response said by (Stronge, 2018).

Harris & De Bruin, (2018) stated that the school environment has great significance in shaping and reshaping intellectual ability and physical fitness of both teachers and the taught. Supportive and favorable school environment helps students to be more comfortable, fully and concentrated on improving their learning activities. Giving stress for provision of conducive environment in the educational institutions Quality of schooling is linked with the qualification of teachers, curriculum, educational materials, teaching methodologies, equipment and physical facilities such as well-designed and well equipped classrooms, laboratories and libraries, furniture, playgrounds, drinking water, electricity, gas, boundary walls, textbooks and teaching aids such as maps, models, audio-visual aids. More and better learning materials will be an essential ingredient in improving the quality of students.

Hébert (2018) school environment has a great influence on students' learning and growth, including their social, emotional and ethical development. The supportive and caring environment of school energized students to be more involved in studies, keeps them away from abuse, violence and other indiscipline or

problematic activities. Positive interpersonal relationship and optional learning opportunities for students in all demographic environments can increase the achievement of students. Good student teacher relationship, positive and supportive school environment helps students for smooth running of academic activities which results in good academic performance. Teachers' professional competency and maintain discipline are the key factors for improving students' academic performance. Students who attend classes under higher caliber of teachers and under controlled discipline can perform better.

Good discipline allows students to work well and this ultimately leads to better academic performance. Serious breaches of school discipline includes assault by students on teachers and other students, verbal abuse ,offensive language against teachers and students, harassment, threat and pressure of teachers and other students, possessing offensive weapons, supplying or using illegal drugs become a case of study that needed immediate attention (Hamm, et al, 2018).

Presentation and Analysis of the Results

Table: 2 School Climate Influences on Students Performance

Sr. No	School Climate	Percentages					Mean	SD
		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA		
1.	Conducive classroom environment affects students' learning.	38.29	51.70	5.59	3.29	1.11	4.23	0.79
2.	School environment is necessary for learning of students.	48.89	40.60	4.40	2.20	3.89	4.28	0.94
3.	Peaceful classroom environment affects students' performance.	52.20	33.89	3.29	7.79	2.79	4.25	1.03
4.	Peaceful School environment is necessary for truthful learning of students.	48.89	42.79	5.59	1.10	1.7	4.36	0.78
5.	Safe and secure school environment affects students learning.	45	38.89	5	3.99	7.20	4.09	1.14
6.	Teaching techniques affect students learning.	46.70	39.39	8.30	3.89	1.7	4.46	3.02
7.	Professional qualification of teachers affects students' performance.	30.10	31.69	25.6	8.30	4.40	4.17	4.5
8.	Peer groups affect students' performance.	24.39	57.20	7.79	5.59	5	3.91	0.99
9.	School environment affects students' social needs.	35	47.79	7.79	7.79	1.7	4.07	0.94
10.	Classroom activities affect students' learning.	42.20	50	4.40	1.7	1.7	4.29	0.77

The data of table 2 shows that most of the male and female respondents (38.29 + 51.70 = 90%) agreed that a conducive classroom environment affects' students learning. It was found that most of the respondents (89.5) agreed to the statement that the school environment is necessary for the learning of the student. It was revealed that majority of the respondents (86.09) agreed to the statement that a peaceful classroom environment affects students' performance. It was shown from the data analysis that most of the male and female respondents (48.89+42.79= 91.68) agreed that peaceful school environment is necessary for truthful learning of students. It was found from the respondents' response that most of the male and female respondents (45+38.89= 83.90) agreed that a safe and secure school environment affects students learning. It was indicated that majority of the respondents (86.09) agreed to the statement that Teaching techniques affect students learning. It was found that most of the male and female respondents (30.10+31.69= 61.79) agreed that the professional qualification of teachers affects students' performance. It was found from the respondents' response that the majority of the respondents (81.59) agreed that peer groups affect students' performance. It was indicated that majority of the respondents (82.79) agreed that school environment affects students' social needs. It was found from respondents' response that most of the male and female respondents (42.20+50= 92.20) agreed that classroom activities affect students' learning.

Sr. No	School Discipline	Percentages					Mean	SD
		SDA	DA	UD	A	SA		
1.	Student's absenteeism from school affects their performance.	58.29	31.69	3.89	0.59	5.59	4.37	1.00
2.	Preparation of lesson plans affects students' performance.	32.79	52.20	5	8.30	1.7	4.05	0.92
3.	Mal practices during examinations affect students' performance.	37.29	40	11.69	6.70	4.40	4.21	3.24
4.	Illegal funds collection affects students' performance.	23.30	44.39	16.69	10	5.59	3.70	1.10
5.	School discipline affects students' personality.	43.30	46.70	5.59	3.29	1.10	4.28	0.80
6.	Good behavior between school and society affect students' learning.	40.60	49.40	3.89	3.89	2.20	4.21	0.86
7.	Teacher students' relationship affect students' performance.	65	23.30	5	4.40	2.20	4.44	0.94
8.	School visits affect students' performance.	17.80	48.89	14.4	15	3.89	3.62	1.06
9	Teachers' attitude affects students learning.	68.29	22.80	3.89	2.20	2.79	4.51	0.89

Table: 3 School Discipline Influence on Students Performance

Table 3 indicates that most of the male and female respondents (58.29+31.69= 90) agreed that student's absenteeism from school affects their performance. It was confirmed that the majority of the respondents (85) agreed to the statement that the preparation of lesson plans affects students' performance. It was found from the respondents' response that most of the male and female respondents (37.29+40= 77.29) agreed that malpractices during examinations influences on students' performance. It was indicated that majority of the respondents (67.70) agreed to the statement that illegal funds collection affects students' performance. It was shown from the data analysis that most of the male and female respondents (43.30+46.70= 90) agreed that School discipline affects students' personality. It was found from respondents' response that majority of the respondents (90) agreed to the statement that good behavior between school and society affect students' learning. The table 3 shows that most of the male and female respondents (65+23.3= 88.29) agreed that teacher students' relationship effect on students' performance. It was revealed that majority of the respondents (66.70) agreed to the statement that school visits affect students' performance. It was observed from the respondents' response that most of the male and female respondents (68.29+22.80= 91.09) agreed that teachers' attitude affects students learning.

Table: 4 Physical Facilities Influences on Students Performance

Sr. No	Physical Facilities	Percentages					Mean	SD
		SDA	DA	UD	A	SA		
1.	Electricity has a serious effect on students' learning.	55	30	6.70	3.89	4.40	4.26	1.05
2.	Cleanliness affects students learning.	32.79	50	6.09	6.09	5.00	3.99	1.04
3.	Impurity of drinking water affects the students' performance.	43.89	38.29	6.09	8.30	3.29	4.11	1.06
4.	Lack of audio visual aids affects students' learning.	36.70	40.60	9.40	7.79	5.59	3.93	1.12
5	Attractive School building motivates students to learn.	25	41.10	12.80	12.19	8.90	3.60	1.234
6	Lack of school furniture affects students' learning.	32.20	41.70	10.6	11.69	3.89	3.87	1.11

Table 4 reflects that most of the male and female respondents (55+30= 85) agreed that electricity has a serious effect on students' learning. It was indicated that majority of the respondents (82.79) agreed to the statement that cleanliness effects are students learning. It was confirmed from respondents' response that most of the male and female respondents (43.89+38.29= 82.19) agreed that impurity of drinking water affects the students' performance. It was found that majority of the respondents (77.30) agreed to the statement that lack of audio visual aids affects students learning. It was confirmed from respondents' response that most of the male and female respondents (25+41.10= 67) agreed that attractive school building motivates students to learn. The analysis found that most of the male and female respondents (32.20+41.70= 73.90) agreed that lack of school furniture affects students' learning.

Conclusions

The different measures of school environment like conducive classroom environment, peaceful classroom environment, peaceful school environment, safe and secure school environment, teaching techniques, professional qualification of teachers, peer groups, classroom activities, physical facilities (electricity, drinking water, audio visual aids, school building, school furniture), absenteeism, preparation of lesson plans, malpractices during examinations, illegal funds collection, school discipline affects students' personality, good behavior between school and society, teacher students' relationship, school visits and teachers' attitude affects students' learning.

Recommendations

1. Student absenteeism may be reduced to enhance their performance.
2. Malpractices during examinations by students and teachers may be discouraged in order to better the quality of education.
3. Illegal funds collection must be eliminated.
4. Good behavior between school and society can enhance the effectiveness of students' learning.
5. The government must provide all physical facilities like proper space, classrooms, furniture, toilet blocks, audio visual aids, standard building, boundary walls, pure drinking water points, playgrounds, science labs, computer labs, and electricity connections are of the top priorities.

References

- i. Adelman, C., Ewell, P., Gaston, P., & Schneider, C. G. (2014). *The Degree Qualifications Profile: A Learning-Centered Framework for What College Graduates Should Know and Be Able to Do to Earn the Associate, Bachelor's or Master's Degree*. Lumina Foundation for Education.
- ii. Bendix, R. (2017). *Nation-building and citizenship: Studies of our changing social order*. Routledge.
- iii. Bergstrom, J. C., & Randall, A. (2016). *Resource economics: an economic approach to natural resource and environmental policy*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- iv. Eisner, E. W. (2017). *The enlightened eye: Qualitative inquiry and the enhancement of educational practice*. Teachers College Press.
- v. Entwisle, D. R. (2018). *Children, schools, and inequality*. Routledge.
- vi. Frimpong, E. A., Agyeman, G. A., & Ofosu, F. F. (2016). *Institutional Factors Affecting the Academic Performance of Polytechnic Students in Ghana*. *International Journal of Humanities & Social Science Studies (IJHSSS)*, 2(5), 102-109.
- vii. Hamm, M. S., Madison, B. V., & Murnane, R. P. (2018). *The Rubric Meets the Road in Law School Program Assessment of Student Learning Outcomes as a Fundamental Way for Law Schools to Improve and Fulfill Their Respective Missions*.
- viii. Harris, A., & de Bruin, L. (2018). *An international study of creative pedagogies in practice in secondary schools: Toward a creative ecology*. *Journal of Curriculum and Pedagogy*, 1-21.
- ix. Hébert, T. P. (2018). *An Examination of High-Achieving First-Generation College Students From Low-Income Backgrounds*. *Gifted Child Quarterly*, 62(1), 96-110.

- x. Heydarian, A., Carneiro, J. P., Gerber, D., Becerik-Gerber, B., Hayes, T., & Wood, W. (2015). *Immersive virtual environments versus physical built environments: A benchmarking study for building design and user-built environment explorations*. *Automation in Construction*, 54, 116-126.
- xi. Johnson, M. W. (2018). *“There’s nothing wrong with doing something good” : a phenomenological study of early elementary black males’ understanding of heroes, role models and citizenship (Doctoral dissertation)*.
- xii. Khoza, J. F. (2012). *The relationship between the school principals' instructional leadership role and the academic performance of pupils in Swaziland primary schools (Doctoral dissertation)*. <http://uir.unisa.ac.za/handle/10500/13245>
- xiii. Kiprop, C. J. (2012). *Approaches to management of discipline in secondary schools in Kenya*. *International journal of Research in Management*, 2(1), 120-139.
- xiv. Lochner, L., Wieser, H., Waldboth, S., & Mischo-Kelling, M. (2016). *Combining traditional anatomy lectures with e-learning activities: how do students perceive their learning experience?*. *International journal of medical education*, 7, 69.
- xv. Mick, Zais.(2011). *South Carolina School Environment Initiative*. South Carolina Department of Education, Columbia. Retrieved on March 21, 2012, from <http://ed.sc.gov/agency/ac/Student-InterventionServices/documents/SC-SchoolEnvironmentRFP-Nov2011.pdf>
- xvi. Nwonyuku, K. (2018). *The Role of Guidance and Counselling in Performance of Post-Primary Education in Nigeria: Regulatory and Theoretical Perspectives*.
- xvii. Shanjiko, F. A. (2017). *Faculty of Education (Doctoral dissertation, St, Augustine University of Tanzania)*.
- xviii. Sithole, F. (2017). *Strategies to enhance teacher motivation in satellite secondary schools in the resettlement areas of Matabeleland North Province (Doctoral dissertation)*.
- xix. Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers*. ASCD.